

The illumination - ball as light source

Harald Schröer

2015

We have a ball with radius R as light source. r is the distance between the midpoint of the ball and the point p , see figure.

We search the illumination in p . First we assume that the whole room is vacuum.

The positions of p and B are

$$\vec{p} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ r \end{pmatrix} \quad \vec{B} = R \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sin \beta \cos \gamma \\ \sin \beta \sin \gamma \\ \cos \beta \end{pmatrix} \quad 0 \leq \beta \leq \alpha$$

with spherical polar coordinates see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §3 (3.6) p.33. The illumination is constructed with the distance $\sqrt{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \beta}$:

$$\vec{E} = \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{R^2 w}{(r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \beta)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -R \sin \beta \cos \gamma \\ -R \sin \beta \sin \gamma \\ r - R \cos \beta \end{pmatrix} d\gamma d\beta \quad (1)$$

R is the Gram determinant's root of both integrals. w is the surface luminous intensity density with the relation $I = 4\pi R^2 \cdot w$.
 I = luminous intensity of the ball

integration over γ :

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \begin{pmatrix} -R \sin \beta \cos \gamma \\ -R \sin \beta \sin \gamma \\ r - R \cos \beta \end{pmatrix} d\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ (r - R \cos \beta) \cdot 2\pi \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

It follows:

$$\vec{E} = 2\pi R^2 w \cdot \int_0^\alpha \frac{r - R \cos \beta}{(r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \beta)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} d\beta \quad (3)$$

$r > R$

It is unknown, if (3) can be represented without integrals.

Now a medium is in the whole room with constant density and constant absorption coefficient m . Then we obtain the illumination:

$$\vec{E} = \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{R^2 w \cdot e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+R^2-2rR \cos \beta}}}{(r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \beta)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -R \sin \beta \cos \gamma \\ -R \sin \beta \sin \gamma \\ r - R \cos \beta \end{pmatrix} d\gamma d\beta \quad (4)$$

The integration over γ can be calculated in the same way as in (2). Then it is:

$$\vec{E} = 2\pi R^2 w \cdot \int_0^\alpha \frac{(r - R \cos \beta) \cdot e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+R^2-2rR \cos \beta}}}{(r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \beta)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} d\beta \quad (5)$$

$$r > R$$

For (5) a representation free of integrals is unknown.

An approximation for $r \gg R$:

$$\vec{E} \approx \frac{I}{r^2} \cdot e^{-mr} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now we treat an example with $R=1$ metre and the luminous intensity 1 candela. We calculate the illumination in dependence of the distance. We use the following table with the illumination in lux:

r [metre]	$E_z = \vec{E} $ exact	$E_z = \vec{E} $ approximation
2	0.3279	0.2500
3	0.1162	0.1111
4	0.05985	0.06250
5	0.03656	0.04000
6	0.02466	0.02777
7	0.01777	0.02041
8	0.01341	0.01563
9	0.01048	0.01235
10	0.008419	0.01000

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001